

ON THE ROLE OF WATER CONTAINED IN THE SOLVENT USED IN FILTER PAPER CHROMATOGRAPHY. PART I

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Rates of movement (R_f values) of the amino-acids in paper chromatography with isopropyl alcohol-water of various compositions have been determined. R_f values have been observed to gradually increase with the increase in water content of the system and finally merge into the values obtained with pure water. The differentiation between the individual amino-acids, however, decreases with increase in water content of the solvent. isoPropyl alcohol containing 30% water by volume has been found to be a suitable second solvent for two-dimensional paper chromatography of amino-acids.

Consden, Gordon and Martin (*Biochem. J.*, 1944, 38, 224) observed that the R_f values of amino-acids (rates of movements of the amino-acids/rate of movement of the solvent front) change in the direction of the water – solubility of the solvent in case of a homologous series of partially miscible solvents. During the separation of phosphoric esters with water-miscible solvents, Hanes and Isherwood (*Nature*, 1949, 164, 1107) observed that changes leading to increased water content of the flowing solvent increased the R_f values but at the same time decreased the differentiation between the individual esters. The same type of observation was made earlier by Jermyn and Isherwood (*Biochem. J.*, 1949, 44, 402) in case of sugars. Bentley and Whitehead (*ibid.*, 1950, 46, 341) while studying a number of water-miscible solvents for their use in two-dimensional chromatography, supported the views of Hanes and Isherwood (*loc. cit.*). Thus the water content of the solvent employed governs the rates of movements of the substances subjected to paper chromatography. Separation of the substances on the chromatogram entirely depends upon the rates of movement of the individual substances, as such, water content of the solvent has an important bearing upon the paper chromatography. Further, R_f values change with change of temperature according as the water content of the saturated solvent decreases or increases with the variation of temperature (Consden, Gordon and Martin, *loc. cit.*).

In an earlier communication the authors (*Science & Culture*, 1950, 15, 363) observed that with pure water R_f values of different amino-acids and sugars were close to unity but not equal to unity, as expected from the theory of paper chromatography, proposed by Consden, Gordon and Martin (*loc. cit.*). In extending that observation we carried out this study to find out how the rates of amino-acids were affected by the varying amounts of water contained in the solvent employed.

When pure solvents (as phenol, collidine, *n*-butanol, etc.) are run along the paper, no movement of the spots takes place. As soon as some water is mixed with the solvent, the movement starts; the rate of movement increases with the increase in water content of the solvent. In case of a partially

miscible solvent, however, the water content can be varied within the saturation limit only. In order to study throughout a wide range of water content, the completely miscible solvent, isopropyl alcohol, has been chosen by us. The water content of the solvent has been varied from 5% to 95% by volume and the corresponding R_f values of the different amino-acids have been determined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solvent.—Absolute isopropyl alcohol was prepared by refluxing and distilling over quick lime, and was mixed with measured volumes of water. The concentrations stated in Table II refer to percentage by volume.

Apparatus.—Due to high volatility of the solvent, isopropyl alcohol, the chamber employed for paper chromatography should always remain saturated with the vapour and the saturation equilibrium should not be much disturbed. In this respect ascending method of Williams and Kirby (*Science*, 1948, 107, 481) was found to be more convenient than the original descending method. The simple apparatus for ascending paper chromatography consisted of a cylindrical jar (about 32 cm. high and of 20 cm. diam.) inverted on a plate glass. Within it was placed a Petri dish (of diameter of about 16 cm.) which contained the solvent isopropyl alcohol and water in definite proportions; 100 c.c. of the solvent mixture were used for each experiment. For duplicate experiment fresh solvent mixture was employed as the composition of the solvent mixture changed considerably even after single development. Before every experiment the chamber was allowed to saturate for 8 to 12 hours.

Procedure.—A piece of paper (43 cm. × 30 cm.) was cut from Whatman No. 1 filter paper sheet. A pencil line was drawn along the length of the paper, 2 cm. above one edge. Point marks were made by graphite pencil on this line, 2.5 cm. apart from each other. Individual amino-acids were applied on these points by means of micropipettes; the diameter of the drop on the paper being about 2 to 3 mm. The solutions of the amino-acids were made by dissolving 5 mg. of the amino-acids in 2 c.c. of water. Those which were applied on paper as hydrochlorides were neutralised with ammonia vapour before development. The paper was next made into a cylinder, the edge near the line forming the base of the cylinder and the vertical sides were attached without touching each other by means of paper clips. The jar over the Petri dish was removed for a while and the paper cylinder was put undisturbed on the Petri dish, the pencil line near the base remaining a little above the surface of the solvent mixture. The jar was replaced immediately. The solvent-mixture ascended along the filter paper by capillary force. When the solvent front ascended very close to the upper edge, the paper cylinder was taken out, the solvent front was marked with

pencil and then the paper was air-dried. The development-time varied depending upon the composition of the solvent mixture. With higher water content 5 to 8 hours' development was enough. But with lower water content it required 12 to 14 hours. The dried paper was sprayed with ninhydrin solution (0.1 g. dissolved in 100 c.c. of *n*-butanol) and heated at 90°-95° for about 5 minutes. The R_f values of the individual amino-acids were calculated from the corresponding spots developed on the paper.

The R_f values of methionine with *n*-butanol containing varying amounts of water are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Ascending chromatography.

Temp = 25°. Time of run in each case = 24 hours.

Solvent.	Distance moved by the solvent.	Distance moved by the amino-acid.	R_f .
<i>n</i> -Butanol-water (17 : 3)*	28.5 cm.	6.1 cm.	0.21
" (18 : 2)	27.2	4.8	0.17
" (18.5 : 1.5)	27.0	3.0	0.11
" (19 : 1)	27.0	2.2	0.08

*Saturated with water.

The rates of movement of the amino-acids *i. e.* R_f values with *isopropyl* alcohol-water of various compositions are recorded in Table II. The recorded values are averages of 2 to 3 determinations. In no case the values differed by more than 5%. The spots were well-defined in all cases with the exception of arginine and lysine. The spots became streaky in case of these two amino-acids when the water content of the solvent was high. In a few cases diffused tailing or bulging was observed.

During chromatography the solvent front at first descends or ascends very rapidly but after it has reached a certain height its velocity slows down considerably. In order to verify whether rates of movement of the amino-acids (R_f values) were independent of the distance run by the solvent front, R_f values of two amino-acids were determined when the solvent front traversed different distances. The values obtained are recorded in Table III which clearly indicate that whatever might be the distance run by the solvent, R_f values remain almost constant.

TABLE II
R_F values of amino-acids with isopropyl alcohol-water (in various proportions).
 (Ascending chromatography).

isopropyl alcohol Water	100% 0%		95% 5%		90% 10%		85% 15%		80% 20%		75% 25%		70% 30%		60% 40%		50% 50%		40% 60%		30% 70%		20% 80%		10% 90%		0% 100%		
	(% by vol.)																												
Amino-acids.
Phenylalanine	...	0	0.16	0.20	0.35	0.45	0.54	0.57	0.71	0.73	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.81
Glycine	...	0	.03	.04	.09	.16	.25	.30	.52	.63	.74	.79	.80	.82*	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.86
Methionine	...	0	.14	.18	.30	.40	.50	.54	.69	.73	.80	.83	.83	.82*	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.85	.90
Tryptophane	...	0	.04	.08	.19	.27	.36	.41	.57	.57	.62	.60	.60	.59	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.60	.57
Aspartic acid	...	0	0	0	.01	.06	.15	.28	.51	.69	.79	.84	.86	.89	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95	.95
Glutamic acid	...	0	0	0	.01	.09	.19	.32	.57	.70	.80	.86	.87	.90	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94	.94
Leucine	...	0	.31	.33	.46	.54	.60	.64	.78	.80	.85	.87	.86	.88	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90	.90
Threonine	...	0	.03	.06	.14	.22	.30	.40	.59	.71	.80	.82	.83	.87	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92	.92
Alanine	...	0	.07	.08	.17	.26	.36	.43	.57	.73	.80	.84	.84	.87	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88
Serine	...	0	.02	.04	.09	.17	.24	.34	.51	.67	.79	.81	.84	.85	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88	.88
Histidine*	...	0	0	.02	.06	.14	.19	.24	.40	.57	.66	.70	.71	.77	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86	.86
Tyrosine*	...	0	.05	.09	.20	.29	.40	.44	.60	.69	.76	.78	.78	.76	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78	.78
Cystine*	...	0	0	0	0	.03	.07	.14	.30	.51	.63	.76	.77	.80	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89	.89
Arginine*	...	0	0	0	.01	.05	.08	.12	.17†	.21†	.20†	.21†	.21†	.24†	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Asparagine	...	0	0	0	.04	.14	.22	.42	.72	.77	.76	.77	.76	.78	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80	.80
Lysine*	...	0	0	0	.01	.05	.06	.11	.20†	.30†	.28†	.25†	.28†	.36†	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+

Applied as hydrochlorides, neutralised with NH_3 vapour.

† These values are not accurate since the spots were too much streaky.

TABLE III

Ascending chromatography.

 Solvent—*isopropyl alcohol-water* (8 : 2).

Period of run.	Distance run by the solvent front.		R_f value.
	(a) Phenylalanine.		
2 hrs	9.2 cm.	4.3 cm.	0.46
5	16.8	8.5	0.49
12	21.7	10.9	0.50
16	26.2	11.8	0.45
	(b) Threonine		
1½	9.3	2.2	0.23
5	16.4	3.6	0.22
12½	23.8	5.7	0.24
16	26.2	5.8	0.22

DISCUSSION

The variation of the R_f values with the water content of the solvent is clearly indicated in Table II. When absolute *isopropyl alcohol* is used no movement of any of the spots occurs. As earlier stated, with many other solvents the same thing occurs. This might be due to insolubility or sparing solubility of the amino-acids in the pure solvents. This signifies that water is the essential constituent of the solvent used in paper chromatography. When the water content is low (say 5% by volume), rates of movement of most of the amino-acids are very slow, in some cases even nil. With the gradual increase in water content, however, the R_f values gradually increase. With the increase in water content from 10% to 40% by volume, the rate of increase is very rapid in most cases. On raising the percentage of water from 40% to 60% the rate of increase becomes rather slow on the average. With 60% water and above, the R_f values remain practically unchanged and are almost the same as those with pure water. That is why there are found some breaks in the sequence of R_f values at this high percentage of water. The difference in R_f values of an amino-acid with different percentages of water in this region lies within the range of experimental error (which is permissible up to 5%) and the R_f values of the different amino-acids become much close to each other. Therefore, with the gradual increase in water content of the solvent, the R_f values gradually increase and finally merge into the values obtained with pure water but the differentiation between the individual amino-acids gradually diminishes. This is in agreement with the observations of Hanes and Isherwood (*loc. cit.*) and Bentley and Whitehead (*loc. cit.*).

The increase in R_f values with the increase in water-content of the developing solvent is expected from the partition mechanism suggested for paper chromatography. Increase in water-content of the solvent results in increasing the solubility of the solute in the mobile phase which leads to decrease in the value of α , partition coefficient. According to the formula proposed by Consden *et. al.* (*loc. cit.*) R_f value increase with the decrease of α .

Extension to Two-dimensional Chromatography

The study of the R_f values of the different amino-acids with the *isopropyl* alcohol-water mixtures has been helpful in suggesting a second suitable solvent for two-dimensional chromatography.

Phenol-water and collidine-water or pyridine-amyl alcohol-water are the solvents commonly employed for this purpose. Phenol-water and *isopropyl* alcohol-water can be successfully employed for the same. Of the various proportions of water in *isopropyl* alcohol, 30% by volume will be the most suitable one since the difference in the R_f values of the individual amino-acids is maximum at this concentration. A comparison of the R_f values obtained with phenol-water and *isopropyl* alcohol-water (7:3) will at once suggest its use as the second solvent in two-dimensional chromatography.

R_f values of amino-acids with phenol-water and *isopropyl*-alcohol-water (7:3) are shown below.

TABLE IV.

Amino-acids*	Aspartic acid	Glutamic acid	Cystine †	Serine.	Glycine.	Lysine. †	Threonine.	Arginine. †	Alanine.	Tyrosine. †	Histidine. †	Tryptop hane.	Methionine.	Leucine.	Phenylalanine.
R_f values with Phenol-water **	0.22, 0.23, 0.24			0.30 0.36		0.41 0.43		0.54 0.55, 0.55			0.62	0.71 0.74		0.80, 0.83	
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol-water (7:3) (authors)	0.28 0.32 0.14			0.34 0.30		0.11 0.40		0.12 0.43 0.43			0.24	0.41 0.54		0.64 0.57	

The list is not complete due to unavailability of a few amino-acids.

Williams and Kirby (*loc. cit.*).

Applied as hydrochlorides and neutralised with NH_3 vapour.

The values within brackets are close to each other and thus indicate the inseparability of those amino-acids with the single solvent phenol-water. The corresponding values with *isopropyl* alcohol-water, however, signify that a good separation can be effected of those inseparable amino-acids with the exception of alanine and tyrosine, the R_f values of which are identical with each other in case of both the solvents. We have successfully separated known mixtures of amino-acids by two-dimensional paper chromatography using phenol-water as first solvent and *isopropyl* alcohol-water (7:3), as the second.

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